

Nurturing the Next Generation of Women in STEM

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The need to encourage greater female participation in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) is globally recognised as an education priority. The gender gap is most pronounced in mathematics-intensive fields including physics, computer science, engineering and mathematics. Such a gap is influenced by a range of complex and nuanced factors that combine to deter female students from considering STEM careers. These deterrents are in place from early childhood and are encountered across all spheres of influence in girls' lives, including individual, family, school, and wider society. Effective change requires a multi-faceted approach targeting all stages of girls' education. Additionally, a societal and cultural shift is required to help female students overcome existing barriers and ensure greater equality in STEM participation. This paper considers the perspectives of female STEM students who have overcome barriers to entry by choosing to study mathematics-intensive STEM in higher education. Informed by a qualitative research study, the paper explores how students' expectations for success, interests, and sense of belonging in STEM were nurtured during school. The objective is to provide a deeper understanding of how the school environment encourages STEM choices with the aim of informing potential avenues for further research into measures addressing the gender gap.

Keywords: STEM, gender, identity

Introduction

STEM education plays an ever-increasing role in today's world as we face unprecedented challenges. STEM provides the innovative solutions required to tackle challenges in areas such as healthcare, climate change and food security. Additionally, a workforce equipped with STEM skills is needed to ensure continued economic growth and national competitiveness (Dasgupta & Stout, 2014). In recent years the Irish Government, similar to countries worldwide, has placed increased focus on STEM education as Ireland aims to "*become the best education and training service in Europe by 2026*" (Department of Education and Skills, 2017, p. 3). However, statistics for Ireland show a significant gender gap in certain STEM fields where female students account for just 12% of electronics, 19% of software, 25% of physics and 32% of mathematics students (Higher Education Authority, 2023). Similar trends are seen worldwide (e.g. Cheryan et al., 2017). This research study aims to explore what motivates female students to choose STEM and how does the school environment encourage STEM choices.

Choosing STEM: Insights from Literature

Expectancy-value theory posits that achievement related choices are related to the combined influences of expectations for success and values (Eccles & Wigfield, 2020). The theory explains that, in order for female students to choose STEM, they need to believe in their ability to succeed (expectations for success) as well as having high interest (values) in

pursuing STEM. Expectations for success and values develop over time and are shaped by students' previous academic achievements, individual characteristics, personal and social identity and how students perceive others' beliefs and behaviours (Eccles & Wigfield, 2020). Seeds of interest and enjoyment in STEM are set in early childhood and need to be nurtured throughout all stages of the educational journey from pre-school to higher education. At each educational stage, girls face barriers to STEM entry which cumulate from childhood to adolescence resulting in a significant gender gap. Beginning in early childhood, gender stereotypes (Banerjee et al., 2018) suggest that girls don't belong in STEM (Cheryan et al., 2017), or have the ability to succeed in the domain (Eccles & Wigfield, 2020). In turn, this results in girls reporting less interest in and enjoyment of STEM (Eccles & Wang, 2016). Additionally, the factors that influence girls' beliefs and interests in STEM are shaped by messages they receive from home, school and wider society; i.e. the STEM ecosystem (Department of Education, 2020).

Within this STEM ecosystem, the role of the school environment in nurturing female students in Ireland to pursue STEM is underexplored. Through exploring how students' beliefs, interests and sense of belonging were shaped by their school experiences, a deeper understanding of how the school environment can encourage greater female participation in STEM is uncovered.

Research method

A qualitative research design, including semi-structured interviews, was selected as the research method since it facilitates in-depth exploration of how female students' academic beliefs, interests and sense of belonging in STEM were nurtured during school. A volunteer sampling approach (Cohen et al., 2018) was used and students from two universities in the south of Ireland were invited to participate. The criteria for selection were that the research participants were studying mathematics-intensive STEM programmes and were enrolled in, at least, the third year of undergraduate study. This cohort would have completed the Leaving Certificate examination in 2019 or earlier, prior to Covid-19 related adjustments to the examination process. Following the granting of ethical approval by UCC's Social Research Ethics Committee, one-to-one interviews were conducted with 21 students. Table 1 shows participant profiles with interviewees being identified by pseudonyms. The students' programmes of study include: S (physics or computer science); E(engineering) or M(mathematics). Where participants were studying two domains e.g., physics and mathematics, they were listed in both the S(science) and M (mathematics) categories shown in Table 1. As noted, participants were registered with two universities in the south of Ireland - 15 participants were registered with one university and six with the other.

The rationale for the research study was explained to participants at the start of the interview. Expectancy-value theory (Eccles & Wigfield, 2020) provided a guideline for investigating participants' school experiences. Questions explored academic achievements in mathematics-intensive STEM subjects; participants' confidence in their abilities; the development of participants' STEM interests and enjoyment; perceptions of how school and

teachers viewed STEM; and how teachers, family and peers influenced participants' decision to choose a mathematics-intensive STEM field of study in higher education.

Table 1

Profile of Research Participants

Student Pseudonym	STEM Field of Study	Degree or year of undergraduate study	Completed TY	STEM Programmes in TY?	LC Secondary School Type	Higher Level LC subjects
Alex	S	PhD	No	n/a	Mixed	<i>Subjects for Secondary School:</i> Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Geography, Languages
Alice	S	4th	Yes	Exhibition	Mixed	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Irish, English, French, Home Economics
Anne	SE	PhD	No	n/a	Mixed (DEIS)	Maths, Biology, English, French, German, Music, Geography
Caomhe	E	3rd	Yes	Event promoting STEM to females	Mixed	Maths, Chemistry, Agricultural Science, Irish, English, German, Accounting
Caroline	M	4th	No	n/a	Mixed	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths, DCG, Irish, English, French
Clodagh	E	4th	Yes	Campus week	Girls	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths, Irish, English, French, Art
Emily	E	4th	Yes	Campus week for female students	Mixed	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths, English, Home Economics
Jade	M	4th	No	n/a	Mixed	Maths, Chemistry, Biology, Applied Maths, Irish, English, Spanish, Business
Jennifer	E	4th	Yes	Campus week	Mixed (fee paying)	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths, English, Accounting, Home Economics
Kathryn	E	MEng	Yes	Campus Week	Girls	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Irish, English, German, Accounting
Leah	E	4th	Yes	n/a	Mixed	Maths, Physics, Applied Maths, Irish, English, French, History, Geography
Lola	S	4th	Yes	Campus week for female students	Mixed	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Irish, English, French, Art
Madeline	S	3rd	Yes	Company visit	Mixed	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, English, Art
Molly	E	4th	Yes	Campus week for female students	Girls	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Irish, English, German, Home Economics
Natalie	SM	3rd	Yes	Campus week for female students	Mixed (DEIS)	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths, Irish, English, French, Geography
Niamh	SM	4th	Yes	Campus week for female students	Mixed	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Irish, English, German, Accounting
Rose	S	PhD	Yes	Campus week	Girls	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Irish, English, Spanish
Sonia	SM	3rd	Yes	No	Mixed (fee paying)	Maths, Physics, Applied maths, Engineering, Irish, English, French
Sophie	E	4th	Yes	Event promoting STEM to females	Mixed (Fee paying)	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Applied Maths, Irish, English, German
Úna	S	3rd	Yes	Campus week	Mixed (DEIS)	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Irish, English, Spanish
Zoe	E	MEng	Yes	No	Mixed	Maths, Physics, DCG, Irish, English, German, Geography

Interviews were conducted online via Microsoft® Teams and were typically 50 minutes in duration. Online interviews were found to be an effective means of gathering data given that all participants were familiar with online meeting tools, having spent at least one college semester online during the Covid-19 pandemic. This format allowed students to be interviewed in an environment where they felt comfortable and relaxed. Video recordings of the interviews enabled the researcher to capture participants' unspoken responses and reactions to specific topics. The video recordings were deleted once anonymised transcripts of the interviews were created with each participant being identified via a pseudonym.

Reflexive Thematic Analysis was selected as a method of data analysis since it facilitates “exploring, interpreting and reporting relevant patterns of meanings within a dataset” (Braun & Clarke, 2022, p. 224), whilst still ensuring analysis is sufficiently rigorous to yield credible and meaningful results (Nowell et al., 2017). In this case, the anonymised interview transcripts were inputted to NVivo where the six-phase thematic analysis process was adopted. These are: dataset familiarisation; data coding; initial theme generation; theme development and review; theme refining, defining and naming and write-up (Braun & Clarke, 2022). These phases are non-linear and recursive with themes being actively generated through repeated iterations of the data coding to theme naming phases.

Following this process, three themes were generated to capture how students' school experiences impacted their decision to study STEM. These are “STEM as Appropriate” (relating to belonging); “STEM as achievable (relating to expectations for success), and “STEM as attractive” (relating to values).

Findings and Discussion

Within the STEM ecosystem, school experiences play a crucial role in encouraging female students to develop positive attitudes towards STEM, thereby countering barriers to entry that girls face. The research findings and discussion describe how the combination of three factors (themes) determined participants' decision to choose STEM in higher education. While these findings aren't intended to be generalizable across an entire population, it is intended that they provide fresh insight to inform further research for measures addressing the STEM gender gap in second level education.

STEM as Appropriate

Encouraging girls to view STEM as an appropriate career choice involves countering gender stereotypes, encouraging a sense of belonging in STEM (Dasgupta & Stout, 2014), and promoting career awareness.

Jennifer spoke of how she was always interested in STEM subjects and performed well in STEM in school. Thus, she viewed STEM as achievable and attractive. However, it was only when her teacher suggested that she might consider engineering that Jennifer began to view engineering as a “thinkable” (DeWitt & Archer, 2015) option for her. When asked how she came to choose engineering, Jennifer described a conversation with her teacher saying;

He (*teacher*) said, well, do you like math? Have you considered engineering? And I hadn't up until then. Nobody had said it to me, it had never come across my mind because there's no engineers in my family, nobody knew any engineers, you know... and then I was like, oh well, I'm doing all the sciences. I like maths, I like applied maths. Why don't I go down that route? So that's what happened anyway (Jennifer).

In Jennifer's case, even the suggestion of engineering as an appropriate option provided sufficient impetus, alongside her existing academic beliefs and interest in STEM to lead her to choose engineering.

Teacher awareness and promotion of 'Out of School' programmes (Department of Education and Skills, 2017, p. 8) which raise awareness of STEM opportunities can positively impact girls' attitudes. Lola spoke of how her teachers always encouraged students to participate in STEM related events. She became particularly animated when describing her participation in iWish (iWish, n.d.) in Transition Year (TY).

I loved that week..... It was actually very powerful, really kind of impactful, like really made me feel very included, very involved, very like they wanted you there. Like, they're like hello, there is space for you (Lola)

For Lola, the opportunity to meet with female role models encouraged her to view STEM as a welcoming field in which she could find a "space". The positive impact of TY programmes aimed at promoting STEM careers to female students was mentioned by 7/21 participants in this study while a further 5/21 participants spoke of how attending campus weeks piqued their STEM interests.

A notable finding of this research was that all participants spoke of high parental support for their decision to study STEM in higher education. This would suggest that STEM information campaigns need to target not just students, but must equally aim to raise awareness among parents (Department of Education, 2022, p. 9), especially for parents who don't themselves have experience of working in STEM. For example, Úna spoke of how her parents discussed STEM programmes of study with a guidance counsellor.

So they (*parents*) didn't know what it was at the start. But once we kind of went through it with the guidance counsellor, I think rather that understanding of what the course is, they were like, oh it fits you, it kind of sounds like you, you know, and they were full steam ahead then (Úna).

Úna's mention of how her parents felt the course "fit[ted]" her and of how it "sounds like you" shows how her parents helped Úna foster a sense of belonging once they themselves gained career awareness. This example demonstrates the need to align the STEM ecosystem to ensure messages of encouragement from school are reinforced with similar message from home.

STEM as Achievable

Girls lack of confidence and self-efficacy in their mathematics abilities is frequently cited as one of the reasons for the STEM gender gap (e.g. Cheryan et al., 2017; Eccles &

Wang, 2016; O'Rourke & Prendergast, 2021). These beliefs are significantly influenced by parents and teachers, with both underestimating girls' mathematical abilities (McCoy et al., 2022). Additionally, where teachers hold low expectations for their students, this can have a negative effect on student performance (McKown & Weinstein, 2008).

When asked if she was always confident in her mathematics abilities, Alice was explicit in stating that her lack of confidence was attributable to her teachers' lack of confidence in her.

No. In junior cycle, yes, I would have been. In leaving Cert no, because my teacher didn't have confidence in me to be honest. I had a very good class, with lots of girls actually..... Even now, like four years into a physics degree, I still think I'm bad at maths, but I'm obviously not. I still have this thing in my head that I can't do it, but then when I get into it I can (Alice)

Alice further explained that she was in a high achieving mathematics class in school and how her teacher would hand out class test and exam results in order of who achieved the highest marks. She said that mathematics was her worst result in her Leaving Cert (she got a H2) and even though she was excelling academically in University, the belief that she's "bad at maths" persisted. Although she had sufficient self-efficacy in her mathematics ability, her lack of confidence was still shaped by her senior cycle experiences.

On the other hand, Sonia's experience demonstrated how teacher encouragement can raise expectations for success and subsequently performance. She said of her mathematics confidence;

I never really visualized myself getting H1, like I was always thinking H3.....maybe a H2, if I did well. While she (*mathematics teacher*) was saying, "no you could definitely get a H1" and I was like, ok maybe I can get a H1 (Sonia)

Research participants' expectation for success in STEM was found to align to that of their teachers with students who reported having "good" teachers also reporting high academic beliefs. Students' expectations for success grew through their being faced with challenging, but achievable, tasks. Alex described their mathematics class as one where "*I really liked the fact that it was challenging, but also he (teacher) was very helpful and attentive to students' needs so he wouldn't be dismissive*" while Molly spoke of how her teacher;

was just really clear in explaining things... she (teacher) also kind of held the class in a way that the people who were really, really good could go on and they could do extra bits and she could go over and help everybody, but she wasn't overloading the people who weren't getting it (Molly)

Teachers with high self-efficacy themselves are more likely to create a learning environment where they set challenging goals and use teaching practices that increase students' self-efficacy (e.g. Banerjee et al., 2018). Thus, ensuring that teachers have access to continuous professional development may also assist in addressing the STEM gender gap.

STEM as Attractive

There is widespread agreement in the literature that lack of interest and enjoyment in STEM is one of the primary barriers to entry for female students (Banerjee et al., 2018; Eccles & Wang, 2016).

Common amongst all the participants in this study was that their interest and enjoyment of STEM mirrored that of their teachers: *“he was so passionate about it. I think it rubbed off on all of us as well, like we were kind of excited, going into class”* (Úna). Seeing the relevance of STEM subjects in a broader context, beyond the curriculum, was also valued by students. Jade, a mathematics student, described how her mathematics teacher would:

explain the same thing in ten different ways and he was really passionate about maths too... he was able to engage you and stimulate a genuine love of math and numbers into people... he wasn't just talking about maths but his understanding of the universe (Jade)

While Clodagh described how she loved when her teacher would *“talk about things outside the curriculum. He'd branch out a bit.... we'd always be asking him questions even if it was not relevant”*.

An interesting aspect of the findings was that teacher gender didn't have any impact on how students came to view STEM as an attractive career choice. Participants were equally as enthusiastic in describing how positive learning experiences in STEM classrooms increased interest, motivation and enjoyment, regardless of whether their teacher was female or male.

Conclusions

This qualitative research study considered how female students' decision to study STEM in higher education was shaped by their school experiences. Greater female participation in STEM requires encouraging more female students to view STEM as an appropriate, achievable, and attractive career option. Positive classroom experiences nurtured students' academic beliefs and interests in STEM. Career awareness campaigns, such as transition year campus weeks, can significantly influence female students' STEM attitudes in fostering a sense of belonging and heightening STEM interests. Extending STEM career awareness campaigns to include teachers and parents would help reinforce appreciation of wide range of opportunities that STEM careers can offer.

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